

Assessing the Level of Meeting the Training Quality Requirements of Students Graduating From the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology

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Abstract:

This report aims to assess the level of satisfaction of training quality requirements of students and students after graduating from the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology. Study and investigate, survey 300 former students and 300 employers, the results show the level of meeting the quality of education and training for employers of each department and the whole school: Faculty of Economics finance - Finance 79.52%; Faculty of Science - Engineering 76.55%; Faculty of Administrative Law 75.55%; The whole school 76.89%
Keywords: Evaluation; response level; education quality.

1. Introduction

The world is entering the new millennium with the explosion of information, rapid development of high technology, knowledge economy and globalization trend. The Party and the State advocated to promote industrialization and modernization, implement the strategy of rich people, strong countries, fair, democratic and civilized society. In this context, higher education, with its main role in training and developing human resources, needs to have a great development, especially in terms of quality. With such a clear orientation, from the past decade, higher education has begun a process of self-renewal, higher education has undergone dramatic changes with strong development both in scale and model. and type of training. However, in the development process, the quality of higher education is still inadequate. The quality of training is still low compared to the current socio-economic development requirements.

Training quality is a matter of concern not only for educational managers, lecturers, and students but also for the whole society. Training to meet the requirements of society is the goal of today's colleges and universities. In recent years, Dien Bien College of Economics - Engineering also emphasizes this issue and is specific in the annual quality objectives of the University and the specialized departments. However, the survey to get useful feedback from the former students and employers to adjust the training activities still has certain limitations: The content of the questionnaire is not scientific; The analytical results have not shown the level of meeting the specific training quality requirements for each department; There are no recommended measures to improve and improve the quality of education and training. From those reasons, we chose to study the topic "Assessing the level of meeting the quality of training requirements of graduates of Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology".

2. Research overview

Graduates are the products of education that are "circulated" in society. The product of education is very special, that is Man, is modern Manpower. The assessment of the quality of this particular product is not easy, because there are factors that see immediate results but also many things need time for testing and challenges. It is impossible to measure only the quality of education through the number of graduates, the number of students working or unemployed after graduation, although these are also indicators of quality, but must also be measured through the responsiveness to the work of students when they graduate, the level of satisfaction of employers using employers. There are also opinions that it is possible to design exams to assess the general ability of learners, but in fact, each exam can only be used to assess in each field (eg, economics), and it is difficult to have a shared exam for very different areas such as between humanity and society. Moreover, general competency assessments will make the school less attentive to professional training, contrary to the goal

of specialized training of education. In the world, depending on the model of higher education of each country, different methods of quality assessment and education quality management are applied. The approach of assessing the quality of higher education through product assessment (outcome assessment) is widely used in the world because of the unique nature of educational products.

The relationship between training and use of graduates is a dialectical relationship between service providers and service users. College, university is the place to train human resources, prepare human resources both in terms of structure, quantity and quality to serve socio-economic development needs. Units using college and university graduates use the products of universities - trained personnel. The production does not develop, the schools will no longer exist and vice versa, the schools do not develop, the professions in the society also stalled. One of the secrets to creating great economic achievements in industrialized countries is the close cooperation of schools with employers. The two-way relationship between colleges, universities and employers is also reflected in the fact that colleges and universities are an important information channel to promote the brand of enterprises, on the contrary, The development of the business affirms its position for a school in the labor market.

In terms of benefits, the relationship between well-established graduates and training will benefit both sides. Specifically: The relationship between training and use of graduates contributes to improving training effectiveness. Enhance efficiency in training, thanks to grasping training needs and orders of enterprises that training institutions have plans to direct the procurement of teaching equipment, laboratories and practice workshops. to suit the objectives and content of the training program, contributing to the effectiveness of investment funding. Learners who have a working address after graduation, shape their work after graduation will have stimulating motivation in learning, peace of mind and try to study well; Enhance the outside effectiveness of training: The percentage of graduates with jobs will be increased, skills and knowledge for students are closer to reality and students are more adaptable. As a result, time to find work and adapt to work shortened.

The relationship between training and use of graduates helps to enhance the conditions of training quality assurance, through the participation of graduates using the graduates to build chapter goals and content. The course involved in teaching, supporting or sharing physical and financial facilities, improving the organization of checking and assessing the quality of output, and at the same time, thanks to close relationships with the users Employers, university colleges also have management innovations. Training units are fully aware of the role and importance of employers in improving the quality and effectiveness of training, with respect to the existence and development of training institutions. In contrast, because they are involved in the process of creating products of training institutions, employers will be proactive in their future human resources and at the same time have appropriate workers. more than the need to use, better meet the actual work. The more society develops, the more closely and explicitly the relationship between training and graduate employment. In nearly 20 years, the recruitment of employees of most agencies, enterprises, enterprises, foreign organizations, ... are made public and widely disseminated. Every year, there are thousands of graduates at the training levels participating in the "army" to find work and also hundreds of businesses need to recruit people. However, the fact is that many people do not have jobs or do jobs that are not properly trained, while many businesses find it difficult to recruit people in accordance with the requirements. This situation causes a lack of local redundancy in human resources, causing waste not only on the state resources, people's money but also wasting time and opportunities of learners. This fact shows the link between the school - where training and businesses - where the training of products is very loose. Improving this relationship is an effective solution to improve the training quality of training institutions and improve their ability to respond to the job of graduates, increasing the efficiency of use by students. graduating.

3. Research methods

The study organized a survey of 300 graduates and 300 employers through questionnaires for the period 2015 - 2018:

- + Corporate Accounting, Banking and Finance (Faculty of Economics - Finance).
- + Law, Administrative Office (Faculty of Law - Administration).
- + Cultivation, Livestock - Veterinary (Faculty of Science - Engineering)

Using SPSS to process data and indicate the level of meeting the training quality requirements of 3-year and 3-year graduates of the University, thereby proposing a number of measures to improve the quality of education and training to meet Social needs of 03 departments and schools.

The questionnaire consists of 26 closed questions that are rated on Good, Fair, Average and Weak scale. For statistics, the convention of scoring points is as follows: Very good = 5; Good = 4 points; Good = 3 points; Average = 2 points; Weak = 1 point. Therefore, the total score of the questionnaire will range from 26 to 130 points, corresponding to the satisfaction level of graduates and employers on the training quality of the school, ranging from 0% - 100%. Assessment scores range from 1 to 5.

4. Research results

Table 01: Statistics of total points and average assessment points of the whole school

content	overall		Labor users		Graduated students	
	Point evaluation	total score	Point evaluation	total score	Point evaluation	total score
Total votes	468	468	224	224	244	244
The average value	3.84	99.96	3.84	99.95	3.84	99.96
Outstanding numbers	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00
Standard deviation	0.93	24.21	0.93	24.40	0.92	24.09
Smallest value	1.73	45.00	1.73	45.00	1.73	45.00
Highest value	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00
Total	1799.31	46782.00	861.15	22390.00	938.15	24392.00

Statistical results in Table 01 show:

- The total evaluation score and the average assessment score of employers and graduates have very high similarity, both groups when evaluating and self-assessing give equal average results . This result shows the reliability of the survey results between the two target groups.
- The total average assessment score of graduates and employers on the quality of school training is quite high (Mean = 99.96 points), corresponding to the level of meeting the training quality requirements for users. The school's labor force is 76.89%. Achieving quality targets set out (the school's target for the 2013-2014 school year to meet the quality requirements of training quality is 75%)
- The highest rated score reaches 130.00 points (maximum score), corresponding to 100% of the school's training quality requirements for employers.
- The lowest rated score reaches 45.00 points, corresponding to the satisfaction level of students about teaching activities of teachers / lecturers is 34.61%

- The average score is quite good (Mean = 3.84), the highest average score reaches Very good 5.00, the lowest average score reaches the average of 1.73. Standard deviation (Std. Deviation = 0.93 points).

Table 02: Statistics of total scores and average assessment points of faculties.

content	Kinh tế - TC		Khoa học - KT		Luật - HC	
	total score	average score	total score	average score	total score	average score
Total votes	147		174		147	
The average value	103.38	3.97	99.55	3.82	98.22	3.77
Outstanding numbers	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00
Standard deviation	20.56	0.79	22.83	0.87	28.72	1.10
Smallest value	52.00	2.00	52.00	2.00	45.00	1.73
Highest value	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00	130.00	5.00
Total	15198.00	584.54	17323.00	666.27	14439.00	555.35

Statistics results in Table 02 show:

- The Faculty of Economics - Finance has the highest average score and average assessment score (Mean = 103.38; 3.97), corresponding to the level of training quality requirements for employers of 79, 52%. Achieving the set quality targets (the school's target for the academic year 2013-2014 on the level of meeting the quality requirements for training quality is 75%).

- The Faculty of Science - Engineering has average average score and assessment score (Mean = 99.55; 3.82), corresponding to the level of training quality requirements for employers of 76.57%. Achieving the set quality targets (the school's target for the academic year 2013-2014 on the level of meeting the quality requirements for training quality is 75%).

- The Faculty of Law - Administrative has the lowest average overall score and the average assessment score (Mean = 98.22; 3.77), corresponding to the level of training quality requirements for employers of 75.55%. Achieving the set quality targets (the school's target for the academic year 2013-2014 on the level of meeting the quality requirements for training quality is 75%).

However, the training quality of all 3 faculties has been evaluated fairly well by the graduates and employers, reflected in the average rating ranging between Fair and Good (average assessment score). ranges from 3.77 to 3.97).

Table 03: Summary of evaluation forms of graduates and employers on the quality of the school's training

N ₀	Evaluation criteria	Degree evaluation					Average score
		1	2	3	4	5	
	About Knowledge						
1	Understanding of economic and social fields	14	64	104	171	115	3.66

2	Understanding of professional knowledge	14	69	101	153	131	3.67
3	Ability to apply knowledge learned in real work	18	55	105	150	140	3.72
4	Ability to use foreign languages at work	34	82	105	118	129	3.48
5	Ability to use informatics at work	24	43	110	151	140	3.72
About Skills							
6	Ability to organize and work in teams	16	71	98	145	138	3.67
7	Ability to organize and organize work	4	66	114	149	235	3.73
8	Ability to communicate information (using language, gestures, images, support tools ...)	5	60	116	149	138	3.75
9	Communication ability (Expressed in attitude, style in behavioral communication)	4	48	110	167	139	3.83
10	Ability to self-study and self-study to improve professional qualifications	2	65	116	138	147	3.77
11	Ability to analyze and synthesize data	2	65	106	152	143	3.78
12	Ability to self-deploy work requests from superiors	0	67	112	156	136	3.75
13	Creative ability to solve work	0	64	112	156	136	3.77
14	Ability to solve real work situations	0	55	114	155	143	3.82
15	Understanding the operating environment of the agency	4	55	97	167	145	3.84
16	Ability to absorb, listen to suggestions from colleagues and superiors	0	41	122	160	145	3.87
17	Ability to adjust behavior (language, gestures, attitudes) to adapt to the working environment.	0	51	102	163	152	3.88
18	Ability to build and develop relationships with the collective	0	52	108	161	147	3.86
19	Ability to search and exploit useful	0	49	108	154	157	3.89

	information on the internet.						
	About Attitude						
20	Enthusiasm in the work	0	23	109	151	185	4.06
21	The attitude positively contributes to your organization (expressed at the level of readiness to work, not afraid of difficulties, working hard for the benefit of the organization).	0	27	103	160	178	4.04
22	Sense of thrift practice in the quarter	2	29	108	148	181	4.01
23	Conscious of organizing labor discipline and respecting the rules of agencies and enterprises	0	21	110	152	185	4.07
24	Conscious, progressive, eager to learn, creative at work	0	31	96	167	174	4.03
25	Spirit of cooperation and help colleagues	0	23	87	174	184	4.10
26	Careful, hardworking at work	0	20	111	155	182	4.06

Statistical results are shown in Table 03:

- The attitude of students who have graduated with assigned jobs, sense of discipline, creative learning in the performance of the most appreciated tasks, the average score reaches Good (> 4.0).
- The use of knowledge and skills learned in assigned work is underestimated, the average score of the assessment ranges from 3.48 to 3.89, in which the point of ability to use professional knowledge and knowledge Other complementary methods reach 3.48 - 3.72. Among the skills asked, organizational skills and teamwork were lowest (3.67%).

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The study has surveyed 224 employers and 244 students have graduated in the training quality of 3 faculties and schools. Processing data and indicating the level of meeting the quality of education and training requirements for employers of each department and the whole school: Faculty of Economics - Finance 79.52%; Faculty of Science - Engineering 76.55%; Faculty of Administrative Law 75.55%; The whole school 76.89%.

Based on the survey results and current school activities, we boldly propose the following solutions to improve the quality of employers' surveys and the quality of education create the school in the future:

***) Periodically improve the training program**

Once every 3 years, the school reviews and improves the training program, in which it is necessary to consider and refer to the results of the employers' survey on the quality of education and training of the school, especially the need for attention. focus on building the content of the program in line with reality, focusing on practicing the theoretical content.

***) Increase the amount of practice and practice**

The actual visit, practice and practice of the theoretical learning contents is very necessary to help learners to be surprised when working out so based on the content and nature of each subject and discipline departments

allocate time to study theory with appropriate practice while attaching importance to building practical practical lectures in association with specific disciplines and occupational realities.

*) Focus on learning service

In addition to the facilities of classrooms and support facilities, the school needs to strengthen the references and books in the library to serve the learning and research of learners. The student management department works more closely with students to capture and solve students' requirements quickly.

*) Organize supplementary classes before going to practice

Schools should organize supplementary classes for students at the end of the course, which provide them with a certain understanding of the working environment of agencies or businesses to help them integrate faster in their places. practice or work.

*) Improve the awareness of studying and exam for students

In addition to caring about the content and teaching methods, the school needs to further improve the management of students in the sense of learning and innovation of examinations and tests to improve the sense of discipline for students in the school. study from there to improve the quality of learning.

*) Regularly consult the recruitment agency

Every 3 years, the school organizes a survey of employers to consult the employers' opinions about the training quality of the school, thereby serving as a basis for chapter improvement. training program to meet social needs.

When surveying, it is necessary to attach importance to the design of scientific questionnaires, organize appropriate ballot papers and handle accurate data in order to obtain high-value results.

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